

1 **The role of canola, black caraway, and wheat bran protein isolates in** 2 **anthocyanin microencapsulation via double emulsions**

3 Havva Aktaş¹, Jorge Custodio-Mendoza¹, Małgorzata Moczowska-Wyrwisz², Arkadiusz
4 Szpicer¹, Marcin A. Kurek¹

5 1. Department of Technique and Food Development, Institute of Human Nutrition Sciences,
6 Warsaw University of Life Science-SGGW, Poland

7 2. Department of Food Gastronomy and Food Hygiene, Institute of Human Nutrition Sciences,
8 Warsaw University of Life Science-SGGW, Poland

9 Corresponding author: marcin_kurek@sggw.edu.pl

10 **Abstract**

11 This study investigates the potential of protein isolates from canola (*Brassica napus* L. var.
12 *napus*) (CC) and black caraway (*Nigella sativa*) (NS) oil cake and wheat bran (*Triticum*
13 *aestivum*) (WB) as sustainable alternatives to traditional soybean isolates (SB) for anthocyanin
14 microencapsulation in double emulsions, aiming to leverage agricultural by-products for
15 sustainable food processing, potentially offering improved functionality for sensitive
16 compound stabilization. The study discovered that NS concentrates considerably improved
17 emulsion stability (ES) (75.89%, 77.26%, 85.09%) in samples when compared to other isolates.
18 SB produced the lowest (1.17 span) and most consistent droplet diameters. Each of the protein
19 isolates under investigation exhibited commendable efficiencies in the encapsulation of
20 anthocyanins. However, the isolates derived from soybean distinguished themselves by
21 achieving the highest encapsulation efficiency, suggesting that they possess intrinsic properties
22 that may not be fully paralleled by the alternative protein sources examined. FT-IR spectroscopy
23 revealed varied secondary structural compositions among the isolates, corresponding to their
24 functional capabilities in emulsion system. This study helps to generate innovative functional
25 foods and fosters the circular economy by successfully encapsulating and stabilizing
26 anthocyanins.

27

28 **Keywords:** Agricultural by-products; protein isolates; anthocyanin encapsulation; plant-
29 based emulsifier

30 1. Introduction

31 The worldwide drive to accomplish sustainable food production has sparked interest in
32 agricultural byproducts as a source of useful ingredients. The valorization of such by-products
33 not only reduces environmental effects but also tackles the essential issue of food waste
34 management in the agricultural business [1]. Food emulsions, which serve as a foundation for
35 introducing health-promoting bioactive chemicals such as anthocyanins into diverse food
36 matrices, are a critical use of these by-products [2,3].

37 Anthocyanins are naturally occurring flavonoids with strong antioxidant properties that have
38 been related to a variety of health advantages, including cardioprotective and anti-diabetic
39 properties [4]. Despite their promise, anthocyanins are difficult to incorporate into food
40 products due to their intrinsic volatility in the face of environmental conditions such as pH
41 fluctuations, oxidative stress, and thermal processing [5]. These circumstances may lead
42 anthocyanins to degrade significantly, resulting in color loss and reduced nutritional and health
43 advantages. The structural modifications that anthocyanins undergo, such as isomerization and
44 polymerization, which can affect their chromatic and antioxidant characteristics, are typically
45 linked to their instability [6,7]. Furthermore, interactions of anthocyanin with other food matrix
46 components might hamper their stability and efficient delivery. Microencapsulation,
47 particularly using water in oil in water (W1/O/W2) double emulsions, has been identified as a
48 potential method for improving the stability and bioavailability of these sensitive components
49 [8].

50 Traditional emulsifiers, which are frequently generated from animal sources or synthetic
51 methods, are increasingly being scrutinized for their environmental and health implications [9].
52 Canola (*Brassica napus* L. var. *napus*) and black caraway (*Nigella sativa*) oil cake and wheat
53 bran (*Triticum aestivum*) were chosen as plant protein isolate sources because of their
54 sustainability and nutritional value. These isolates are not only environmentally friendly, but
55 they are also thought to have the necessary emulsifying capabilities for the formation and
56 stabilization of double emulsions, allowing for effective anthocyanin encapsulation due to their
57 unique compositional characteristics. [10–12].

58 The utilization of these agricultural by-products as natural emulsifiers not only fosters
59 sustainable practices but also utilizes their unique amphiphilic nature, which enables them to
60 stabilize oil-in-water interfaces, crucial for effective microencapsulation [13].

61 Herein we investigate the protein isolates from canola cake, black caraway oil cake and wheat
62 bran as natural emulsifiers for stabilizing double food emulsions focusing on anthocyanin
63 encapsulation. These protein-rich agricultural by-products represent a sustainable alternative to
64 conventional emulsifiers such as soybean protein. Canola cake, wheat bran, and black caraway
65 oil cake are byproducts of existing agricultural processes, as opposed to soybean protein, which
66 needs large land and water resources and is frequently linked to deforestation and monoculture
67 practices. Using these byproducts provides value to the agricultural supply chain while also
68 reducing waste and promoting a circular economy [14]. We aim to evaluate their potential to
69 enhance emulsion stability, nutritional value and functional performance. The novelty of the
70 present work is the investigation of CC, NS and WB protein isolates in double emulsion systems
71 that have not been reported yet in scientific literature. This study describes their emulsifying
72 properties and their efficiency in maintaining emulsion stability, with a view to developing new
73 sustainable food ingredients. The results could potentially impact food science and technology
74 in optimizing natural emulsifiers for enhanced bioactive compound delivery in food industry.

75 **2. Materials and Methods**

76 **2.1. Materials**

77 The freeze-dried blackcurrant powder, used in the present work as an anthocyanin source, was
78 obtained from Milo (Milicz, Poland). Byproducts such as canola cake, black caraway oil cake
79 and wheat bran were sourced from local oil and flour producers in Poland. Cakes were obtained
80 as a result of a cold-pressing process, ensuring the retention of nutritional and functional
81 qualities in the byproducts. Grapeseed oil, used as the oil phase in the double emulsion, was
82 provided by Basso (S.Michele di Serino (AV) Italy).

83 **2.2. Preparation of protein isolates by the alkaline extraction method**

84 The canola cake, black caraway oil cake and wheat bran were each subjected to extraction with
85 hexane at a ratio of 1:5 (w/v). Each sample was agitated for two hours at room temperature
86 (21°C) to ensure thorough mixing and maximum extraction efficiency. After agitation, the
87 mixtures were centrifuged separately to facilitate the separation of the liquid phase from the
88 solid materials. The supernatants were carefully removed, and the remaining pellet, containing
89 the solid residues, were allowed to air dry overnight. Then, 150 mL of deionized water and 10
90 g of defatted seed cake flour were combined separately for the protein isolation. After adding
91 0.1 N NaOH to bring the pH of the slurry to 10, they were stirred for one hour at 400 rpm.

92 Throughout the alkali extraction process, the pH of each slurry was maintained. After the
93 agitation was complete, the slurry was centrifuged at 9 000 rpm for 20 minutes, and the
94 supernatant was collected. Deionized water was used to suspend the leftover residue, and the
95 same extraction procedure was repeated.

96 Based on literature knowledge, pH of combined supernatants was adjusted to isoelectric point
97 with 0.1 N HCl: Canola cake (CC): 4.0; black caraway oil cake (NS): 3.85; Wheat bran (WB):
98 4.4 [15–17].

99 The protein precipitate was separated by centrifugation at 9 000 rpm for 20 minutes, then it was
100 re-suspended three times in deionized water, pelleted, and its pH was adjusted to 7 using 0.1 N
101 NaOH in the last resuspension. Before analysis, the protein extract was freeze-dried (Christ
102 LSC, Germany), vacuum-packed in polyethylene bags, and kept at 20 °C.

103 **2.3. Extraction of anthocyanin from blackcurrant powder**

104 A 50 milliliter solution of methanol and 1% hydrochloric acid (MeOH:HCl) was prepared and
105 combined with 1 gram of lyophilized blackcurrant powder. This mixture was subjected to
106 microwave-assisted extraction based on the modified method described by Chandrasekhar et
107 al. [18]. The extraction parameters were set to a power of 90 watts for a duration of 5 minutes.
108 Following the extraction process, the solvent was removed by evaporation, leaving the extract
109 dissolved in distilled water. The resultant solution was then filtered to remove any residual
110 particulate matter.

111 **2.4. Double Emulsion Preparation**

112 The W1/O/W2 emulsions were prepared with minor modifications using the two-step process
113 described by Sobti et al., [19].

114 **2.4.1. Inner W1/O Emulsion Preparation**

115 The W1/O emulsion was created by combining 50% blackcurrant extract (W1) with 50%
116 grapeseed oil, along with 4% polyglycerol polyricinoleate (PGPR) relative to the oil phase. The
117 dispersion process was conducted using a ULTRA-TURRAX homogenizer (T18, IKA®-
118 Werke GmbH & Co. KG, Staufen, Germany) set at 15,000 rpm for a duration of 10 minutes.
119 The cooling during the emulsification process was meticulously maintained to ensure the
120 stability and consistency of the W1/O emulsion.

121

122 **2.4.2. W1/O/W2 Emulsion Preparation**

123 The W1/O emulsion prepared above was combined with the outer aqueous phase (W2) in a
124 ratio of 40% W1/O to 60% W2. The W2 phase consisted of either protein isolate solutions in
125 three different ratios or a control solution.

126 To prepare the protein solutions for W2, the protein isolates used included soy protein isolates
127 (representing commercially available protein isolates), canola cake protein isolates, black
128 caraway cake protein isolates, and wheat bran protein isolates, in concentrations of 6%, 8%,
129 and 10%. The control solution contained 2% Tween 80.

130 Each specified amount of protein isolate was dissolved in distilled water to prepare the protein
131 solutions. These solutions were then subjected to magnetic stirring for two hours. To inhibit
132 microbial growth, sodium azide at a concentration of 0.02% (w/v) was added. The solutions
133 were stored overnight at 4°C. The following day, the protein solutions were centrifuged at 7,000
134 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C to separate the clear supernatant, which was then used as the outer
135 aqueous phase (W2).

136 To create the W1/O/W2 double emulsions, the primary emulsion (W1/O) was gradually added
137 to the W2 phase in a 40:60 ratio (W1/O). This mixture was homogenized for 10 minutes at
138 15,000 rpm using a ULTRA-TURRAX homogenizer (T25 D, IKA®-Werke GmbH & Co. KG,
139 Staufen, Germany).

140 The samples were systematically coded to facilitate easy reference. The numerical suffix 6, 8,
141 and 10 corresponds to protein concentrations of 6%, 8%, and 10%, respectively. For example,
142 "SB6" refers to a sample with 6% soybean protein isolate, while "CC10" indicates a sample
143 with 10% canola cake protein isolate.

144 **2.5. Analytical methods for protein characterization evaluation**

145 **2.5.1. Protein content (SPC)**

146 The Bradford assessment was used to determine the soluble protein concentration of protein
147 isolates produced by alkaline extraction. Samples were diluted to achieve protein
148 concentrations between 5 and 100 µg in 100 µl sample volumes in order to be ready for the
149 protein assay. An equal volume of 1 M NaOH was added to each sample in order to dissolve
150 protein isolates easily. Subsequently, 5 mL of dye reagent was added to each sample, and
151 incubation took place for 5 minutes. Finally, absorbance at 595 nm was measured, ensuring
152 evaluation of protein samples within the specified concentration range [20].

153 **2.5.2. SDS-PAGE analysis**

154 Protein isolates were electrophoretically separated on precast polyacrylamide gel (7.5%; Bio-
155 Rad Laboratories, Inc., CA) in the presence of SDS-PAGE and 8 mol/L urea using a Mini-
156 PROTEAN Tetra cell (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc., Hercules, CA). The image of the
157 electrophoretic separation of proteins in polyacrylamide gel was scanned using Image Lab™
158 Software and an electrophoretic visualization and archiving system (Molecular Imager Gel
159 Doc™ XR1; Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc.). For ease of computation, it was assumed that the
160 surface of a single protein strand had a 100% share of the surface of all separated proteins in a
161 particular gel [21].

162 All samples for SDS-PAGE were well mixed in a mixer (B-400; Büchi Labortechnik AG,
163 Flawil, Switzerland) for 10 min with the sampling treatment buffer (buffer: 8 mol/L urea, 2
164 mol/L thiourea, 0.05 mol/L Tris, 3% SDS, 10% glycerol, 75 mmol/L DTT, and 0.1%
165 bromophenol blue, pH 6.8) and denaturated at 95°C for 3 min. Equivalent quantities of proteins
166 (2 mg/mL) were put to polyacrylamide gels and electrophoretically separated for 15 minutes at
167 90 V and 60 minutes at 150 V (running buffer: 25 mmol/L Tris, 192 mmol/L glycine, 0.5%
168 SDS). Following that, the samples were washed in deionized water and stained for 1 hour with
169 the Coomassie Brilliant Blue G250 solution (Sigma-Aldrich, Inc., Saint Louis, MO), followed
170 by 24 hours of washing in de-staining buffer (10% methanol, 7.5% acetic acid).

171 **2.6. Analyzing emulsion characteristics**

172 **2.6.1. Droplet size analysis**

173 The droplet size distribution of emulsions was measured using a wet cell equipped
174 Morphologi® G3SE (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Malvern, UK). With minor adjustments, the
175 measuring technique was based on Karp et al.,[22]. Using a magnetic stirrer (SI Analytics
176 GmbH, Germany), 0.1 mL of sample was diluted in 10 mL of 1% SDS (sodium dodecyl
177 sulphate) solution and gently swirled for five minutes at 300 rpm. Fractionation in SDS led to
178 floc disintegration and decreased interdroplet forces. The sample was allowed to settle for ten
179 minutes in order to eliminate bubbles. Every measurement was done three times. The mean
180 diameter $D [n, 4.3]$ of all particles (μm), the smallest particle size $D [n, 0.1]$ (μm), the mean
181 particle size $D [n, 0.5]$ (μm), and the biggest particle size $D [n, 0.9]$ (μm) were selected as the
182 four parameters to characterise droplet size. During the measurement, all parameters were
183 automatically computed. The span was computed using the following equation (1) to determine
184 the size distribution width:

$$185 \quad SI = \frac{D_{90} - D_{10}}{D_{50}} \quad (1)$$

186

187 **2.6.2. Rheological measurements**

188 Apparent viscosity (η) was chosen to characterize the rheological properties of emulsions [22].
189 A Mars III Rheometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., USA) was utilized to perform
190 measurements on a geometric plate-cone at a consistent temperature of 25 °C. The experiment
191 was run for two minutes, with an imposed shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$) ranging from 0 to 100 s⁻¹. The sample
192 was allowed to rest in the measuring location for five minutes prior to measurement (gap =
193 0.056 mm). Measurements of emulsions were made in triplicate to ensure repeatability. In order
194 to analyse the data, the flow curves were fitted to the Ostwald de Waele rheological model as
195 follows (2) using the appropriate software:

$$196 \quad \tau = K \dot{\gamma}^n \quad (2)$$

197 where k is the consistency coefficient (Pa·sⁿ), τ is the shear stress
198 (Pa), and n is the flow behavior index (dimensionless).

199 **2.6.3. Stability**

200 The stability of the double emulsion samples was assessed by centrifugation of double emulsion
201 and determining the weight of the supernatant component [23]. 7 grams of the freshly produced
202 double emulsion (M_0) were placed in centrifuge tubes, and the mixture was centrifuged
203 (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) for 15 minutes at 5 000 rpm and 20°C. The sample's separated
204 supernatant component (M_1) was weighted, and the relationship between the separated part and
205 the emulsion's starting weight was used to calculate the stability of the mixture:

$$206 \quad \text{Emulsion stability}(\%) = \frac{M_1}{M_0} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

207 **2.6.4. Creaming Index**

208 Creaming of double emulsions was observed during storage at 4°C by measuring total emulsion
209 height (EH) and serum layer height (SH). A separation between the oil phase at the top and the
210 aqueous phase at the bottom was observed by the naked eye as a result of the W1/O/W2
211 emulsion creaming [24]. The creaming index (CI) was calculated using the following formula:

$$212 \quad CI(\%) = \frac{SH}{EH} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

213

214 **2.6.5. Quantification of anthocyanin**

215 The approach from de Almeida Paula et al., [25] was used to quantify the anthocyanins
216 concentration. Each sample was divided into a 1 gram aliquot and placed in a 20 mL volumetric
217 flask. The capacity was then filled with a 95% ethanol–1.5 N HCl solution (85/15). Using a
218 digital spectrophotometer, absorbance values were obtained at 535 nm. The apparatus was
219 calibrated using an ethanol 95%–1.5 N HCl solution (85/15) as well as a blank sample. Equation
220 (5) was derived by extrapolating the received reading.

221

$$222 \quad A_{535} = \varepsilon \times b \times C \quad (5)$$

223

224 where:

225

226 C is the anthocyanin content ($\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$), b is the cuvette's thickness (1 cm), and ε is the absorbance
227 coefficient ($98.2 \text{ L cm} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$).

228 The sample fraction that was analyzed's total anthocyanin content was represented in mg of
229 anthocyanins $\cdot \text{L}^{-1}$.

230 **2.6.6. Efficiency of inclusion**

231 Aliquots of roughly 50 g of the double emulsion were centrifuged at 5 000 rpm for 10 minutes
232 to allow phase separation to occur. Following a 0.45 μm syringe filter (PTFE) filtering of the
233 outer phase, the concentration of anthocyanins was measured by using the methodology of de
234 Almeida Paula et al., (2018), which is detailed in the section "Quantification of anthocyanins."
235 With the use of Eq. 6, the percentage of anthocyanins remained trapped in the inner aqueous
236 phase (W1) was determined to be the inclusion efficiency (IE).

$$237 \quad IE = 100 - \left(\frac{CA2}{CA1} \times 100 \right) \quad (6)$$

238

239 where:

240

241 CA1 is the anthocyanin concentration in the inner aqueous phase taking into account the amount
242 of the molecule introduced originally;

243 CA2 is the anthocyanin concentration found in the exterior aqueous phase.

244

245 **2.6.7. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)**

246 An FT-IR spectrometer (Model NicoletTMiSTM 10, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA)
247 operating in the wavelength range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} was used to conduct the FTIR analysis of
248 protein isolates. Thermo Fisher Scientific's OMNIC software was used to analyze the spectra.

249 **2.6.8. Color determination**

250 The color of the emulsions was measured using the CIE Lab measurement technique using a
251 Minolta CR-400 colorimeter (Konica Minolta Inc., Japan) (measuring area = 8 mm and
252 observer 2°, light source D65). Using the CIELAB color space, the samples' colors were
253 represented as follows: L* stands for lightness, a* for red-green, and b* for blue-yellow. Three
254 mL of freshly produced emulsion samples were placed into a petri dish and set on top of the
255 colorimeter's measuring lens. The color measuring process was run three times.

256 **2.7. Statistics**

257 Significant differences between mean values assessed by one-way analysis of variance were
258 denoted by a $p \leq 0.05$. (ANOVA). At $p \leq 0.05$, the Tukey post hoc test was employed to identify
259 statistically significant results. Statistica 12 software (StatSoft, Inc., Tulsa, USA) was used for
260 this study.

261 **3. Results and Discussion**

262 **3.1. Protein content assessment by Bradford method**

263 The soluble protein content, expressed in milligrams of Bovine Serum Albumin equivalent per
264 gram (mg BSA/g), was determined for CC, NS, and WB samples. The results showed a
265 gradation in the protein solubility of the isolates with WB having the highest protein content at
266 84.42 ± 2.80 mg BSA/g. NS concentrates had a moderately high solubility of 73.39 ± 3.29 mg
267 BSA/g, while CC concentrate had the lowest measured solubility at 60.03 ± 4.78 mg BSA/g. The
268 Bradford assay results reveal a significant difference in the SPC among the various plant protein
269 isolates. The relatively higher protein content observed in the WB samples could be indicative
270 of a higher degree of protein extraction efficiency or a greater presence of inherently soluble
271 proteins in WB compared to NS and CC [26,27]. These results may be related to better protein
272 solubility characteristics for microencapsulation of anthocyanin-loaded double emulsions.
273 Emulsifier performance of protein isolates is frequently connected with their protein
274 concentration, since a greater number of accessible protein molecules may improve the ability
275 to stabilize emulsion droplets [28,29].

276 **3.2. SDS-PAGE**

277 The molecular weight distribution of the soluble proteins in isolates generated from SB, CC,
278 NS, and WB was determined using SDS-PAGE. Figure 1 depicts the protein profiles acquired
279 following electrophoretic separation. Across all samples, distinct protein bands are evident,
280 indicating a diversity of protein sizes. In the study of Shen et al., [30], electrophoresis
281 confirmed the separation of napin and cruciferin in CC isolates, with cruciferin bands at 48–56
282 kDa, 30–40 kDa, and 20 kDa, and napin bands at 17 kDa splitting into 6 kDa and 10 kDa under
283 reducing conditions, indicative of heavy and light chains. In our study, the CC isolate (Figure
284 1) shows prominent bands around 17 kDa, which can be attributed to napin proteins, consistent
285 with Shen et al. [30]. The absence of bands at 48-56 kDa and 30-40 kDa suggests that cruciferin
286 proteins are either not present or are below detectable levels in these isolates. In terms of NS
287 concentrates, it has been shown that multiple bands in the gel, likely corresponding to the acidic
288 (30-35 kDa) and basic (20 kDa) subunits of 11S globulins. Additionally, prominent bands at
289 ~102, 75, 68, and 50 kDa were tentatively attributed to the presence of 7S globulins, whose
290 polypeptide structures are maintained by non-covalent interactions rather than disulfide bonds
291 [31]. WB proteins predominantly exhibit molecular weights (MW) from 55 kDa to 15 kDa,
292 with a substantial proportion around 40 kDa, likely representing WB albumin/globulin in the
293 15-30 kDa range. Our SDS-PAGE results for WB isolates reveal bands predominantly between
294 55 kDa to 15 kDa, with a significant band around 40 kDa, aligning with previously reported
295 molecular weights for wheat bran proteins [32]. The appearance of several bands in the soybean
296 protein lane is predicted, given the well-characterized composition of soy proteins, which
297 comprise a variety of subunits such as glycinin and beta-conglycinin [33]. In our study, the SB
298 isolate shows several bands across a wide range of molecular weights, reflecting the complex
299 composition of soy proteins. Protein profiles for CC, NS, and WB isolates reveal a range of
300 molecular weights, with certain bands appearing to match to those shown in the soybean protein
301 profile. This shows that these plant by-products may include protein subunits with emulsifying
302 capabilities comparable to soy proteins, which are frequently employed in industry for their
303 functional features. Nonetheless, it is crucial to remember that protein conformation, the
304 number of hydrophilic and hydrophobic residues, and other structural features all affect the
305 emulsifying and functional qualities of proteins in addition to molecular weight. Proteins
306 exhibit amphiphilic behavior due to the distribution of hydrophilic and hydrophobic amino acid
307 residues, which is crucial for their emulsifying properties. An appropriate balance of these
308 residues enhances the adsorption of proteins at the oil-water interface, forming a stable
309 interfacial film [34]. Conformational flexibility is another important element that influences
310 protein emulsification. More stable emulsions can be formed by proteins with the ability to

311 modify their shape. This adaptability frequently has greater significance than hydrophobicity
312 alone. For example, globular proteins with higher flexibility spread more effectively at the oil-
313 water interface, enhancing their emulsifying abilities [34,35]. Furthermore, a protein's
314 interfacial performance can be influenced by its primary sequence. The capacity of the protein
315 to adsorb at the interface and maintain emulsions can be impacted by sequence variations, such
316 as the existence of certain hydrophobic or hydrophilic regions. The ability of proteins to
317 emulsify is also influenced by their degree of aggregation. Aggregate-forming proteins have
318 varying effects on the stability of emulsions and the viscosity of the continuous phase. While
319 excessive aggregation can hinder emulsification, regulated aggregation might improve it by
320 creating a more robust interfacial network [36].

321 The strength and sharpness of the bands reveal information about the purity and concentration
322 of proteins in each sample [12,32]. However, because the approach primarily gives qualitative
323 data, the strength of the bands does not always correlate directly with the number or functioning
324 of proteins in emulsion systems. As a result, further investigations, such as amino acid
325 composition analysis, are required to properly understand these emulsifying characteristics of
326 proteins. These findings indicate that the protein profiles of CC, NS, and WB isolates are
327 distinct from each other and from SB, reflecting differences in their protein compositions and
328 potential functional properties. The identification and characterization of these bands,
329 supported by literature, provide a basis for understanding the emulsifying properties of these
330 protein isolates.

331

332

333 **Fig. 1.** The gel image displays the molecular weight markers on the left (Std), followed by the
 334 protein bands for SB, CC, NS, and WB.

335 3.3. FT-IR evaluation

336 The secondary structure of protein isolates from CC, NS, and WB was evaluated using FT-IR.
 337 The spectra, as shown in the graph, show typical absorption bands corresponding to various
 338 secondary structure components. The area under the absorbance peaks, which indicate the
 339 various structural components, was determined and is summarized in Table 1. The alpha-helix
 340 to beta-sheet ratio, a major predictor of protein functioning, was also calculated for each protein
 341 isolate. FT-IR spectroscopy is a useful method for characterizing the secondary structure of
 342 proteins and gaining insights into their functional features, such as emulsification, which is
 343 important for food system applications. The protein's flexibility, stability, and interaction with
 344 other molecules can all be influenced by the alpha-helix to beta-sheet ratio [38,39].

345 The FTIR spectrum revealed distinctive peaks that correspond to diverse secondary protein
 346 structures. In CC concentrates, the beta-sheet content was significant, accounting for 50.32%
 347 of the secondary structure. This high concentration of beta-sheets may imply superior protein
 348 structural stability and stiffness, which may contribute to the resilience of emulsions created

349 using CC concentrates [40,41]. When compared to CC and WB isolates, NS isolates displayed
350 a larger number of random coil structures (61.65%), indicating a more flexible and less
351 organized protein structure. The alpha-helix content was high (17.16%), however the beta-sheet
352 content was lower. The alpha-helix to beta-sheet ratio in NS concentrates was the greatest
353 (1.44), which may directly impact the emulsifying and encapsulating characteristics of these
354 proteins by enhancing flexibility and interaction potential at the oil-water interface[42,43].
355 According to Devi et al.,[44], amide I absorption is the most crucial for secondary structure of
356 proteins studies. Furthermore, the amide shifting seen in our work is more indicative of random
357 coil and alpha-helix conformational changes than of beta-sheet structure.

358 WB isolates have a balanced proportion of beta-sheets (40.41%) and alpha-helices (39.73%),
359 showing that the protein structure is a combination of stiffness and flexibility. The amino acid
360 and peptide side chains exhibited the lowest proportion (2.52%), which might indicate a lower
361 degree of free side chain interactions [45,46].

362 The secondary structure of the protein isolates is crucial in the context of anthocyanin
363 microencapsulation. Because beta-sheets are frequently linked with the production of strong,
364 intermolecular beta-sheet aggregates, which can increase the physical stability of the emulsion,
365 the beta-sheet dominating structure in CC may lead to more stable encapsulation. The larger
366 random coil and alpha-helix contents in NS concentrates, on the other hand, may indicate a
367 better potential for interaction with anthocyanins, albeit at the expense of emulsion stability.
368 Because random coil configurations are flexible and provide accessible binding sites for
369 anthocyanins, whereas alpha-helical structures, despite their rigidity, interact with anthocyanins
370 via hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic effects. These interactions are essential to anthocyanin
371 microencapsulation. Alpha-helical and random coil-balanced proteins offer the best binding
372 sites and structural flexibility for encapsulating and protecting anthocyanins [47]. According to
373 study of Qian, et al [48], for example, the interaction between cyanidin-3-O-glucoside (C3G)
374 and lentil protein isolate (LPI) changed the physicochemical characteristics of the system and
375 improved microencapsulation. WB isolates, with their balanced secondary structure, may offer
376 a balance of stability and interaction potential [49,50].

377

378

379
380 **Fig.2.** FT-IR absorption spectra of protein isolates

381
382 **Table 1.** Secondary structure composition of protein isolates from FT-IR analysis

Samples	Peak (cm ⁻¹)	area of absorbance	secondary protein components(%)
CC	side chain of amino acids and peptides	1609.31	3.35
	beta-sheet	1630.04	50.32
	random coil	1642.57	18.87
	alfa-helix	1651.25	21.53
	beta-sheet	1680.66	5.93
	Total		7.22
	α -helix: β -sheet ratio		0.38
NS	beta-sheet	1627.63	6.29
	random coil	1638.23	61.65
	alfa-helix	1650.29	17.15
	Beta-turn	1670.05	9.28
	beta-sheet	1681.62	5.62
Total		7.90	100.00
	α -helix: β -sheet ratio		1.44
WB	side chain of amino acids and peptides	1607.86	2.52
	beta-sheet	1619.91	12.22
	beta-sheet	1630.04	40.41
	alfa-helix	1649.32	39.73

beta-sheet	1680.18	0.36	5.11
Total		6.96	100.00
α -helix: β -sheet ratio			0.69

383

384 3.4. Analysis of droplet size

385 As shown in Table 3, the Span values, which indicate the width of the size distribution, varied
 386 across samples, with soybean protein isolates (SB6, SB8) demonstrating a narrower size
 387 distribution as evidenced by lower Span values. In contrast, SB10 had the highest Span value
 388 (3.16), indicating a broader distribution of droplet sizes. WB isolates (WB6, WB8, WB10)
 389 showed Span values that did not differ significantly from SB6, SB8, and CC8, indicating
 390 intermediate size distributions. Droplet size and distribution are essential elements in emulsion
 391 stability, with smaller and more evenly distributed droplets frequently associated with improved
 392 stability [51]. The Span values acquired from the study represent the homogeneity of the droplet
 393 sizes, with a lower Span number indicating a more uniform size distribution. Soybean protein
 394 isolates had the most homogeneous droplet sizes, which is consistent with the well-documented
 395 emulsifying capabilities of soy proteins [44].

396 Comparing emulsions stabilized by soybean protein isolates to those stabilized by other plant
 397 protein isolates, it is interesting to note that the CE Diameter average indicates that the former
 398 also tended to have larger droplet sizes. This difference may be attributed to the intrinsic
 399 characteristics of the protein or the processing conditions during emulsification could have
 400 different effects on each protein [52]. Despite having a greater size dispersion in WB6, WB8
 401 and WB10 isolates maintained a low range of droplet sizes. This suggests that, although the
 402 homogeneity of the WB6 emulsion may not be ideal, the overall stability of the emulsion could
 403 still be satisfactory. It may also suggest that the emulsifying capacity of WB proteins might be
 404 improved by modifying the processing conditions or the components used in the emulsion
 405 process. [46]. The findings of the droplet size study might have practical uses in the food
 406 business, where the emulsifying characteristics of plant proteins can be used to create stable
 407 emulsions for a variety of applications.

408 3.5. Viscosity

409 The rheological behavior of the emulsions stabilized by various protein isolates was
 410 characterized using the Ostwald de Waele model, and the parameters τ (shear stress), K
 411 (consistency coefficient), and n (flow behavior index) are presented in Table 2. Additionally,

412 the viscosity and flow curves are displayed in Figures 3 and 4 as supplementary material to
413 provide a comprehensive understanding of the flow characteristics.

414 The viscosity curves of the emulsions show a clear shear-thinning behavior for most samples,
415 where the viscosity decreases with increasing shear rate. This is typical for emulsions, as the
416 internal structure breaks down under shear, allowing the material to flow more easily. The
417 soybean protein isolates (SB6, SB8, SB10) exhibited higher K values, indicating stronger
418 internal networks that resist flow. In contrast, the NS isolates (NS6, NS8, NS10) demonstrated
419 lower K values, suggesting a more fluid-like behavior. WB isolates displayed intermediate K
420 values, with WB6 showing relatively higher viscosity compared to WB8 and WB10, indicating
421 a moderately strong internal network which may favour the formation of a more structured
422 network within the emulsion [12,46]. CC isolates exhibited the lowest K values, such as CC8
423 with $K = 0.01162 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}^n$, suggesting that CC-stabilized emulsions have less resistance to flow
424 and a more fluid-like behavior. The flow behavior index (n) provides insight into the degree of
425 shear-thinning or shear-thickening behavior exhibited by the emulsions. Most samples
426 displayed shear-thinning behavior, with n values less than 1. The soybean protein isolate
427 emulsions, particularly SB10, formed emulsions with higher n values, indicating a strong
428 internal structure that exhibits shear-thinning behavior. This can be attributed to the high protein
429 content and effective emulsifying properties of soy proteins, which form robust networks within
430 the emulsion matrix. In contrast, the NS isolates produced emulsions with lower n values,
431 suggesting a more fluid emulsion with less internal resistance to flow. The rheological analysis
432 of the emulsions reveals significant differences in their flow properties based on the type of
433 protein isolate used. The soybean protein isolates, particularly SB6, formed emulsions with
434 higher consistency coefficient ($K = 0.1946 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}^n$) and flow behavior index ($n = 0.5184$) values,
435 indicating a strong and viscous internal structure. This can be attributed to the high protein
436 content and effective emulsifying properties of soy proteins, which form robust networks within
437 the emulsion matrix [53]. In contrast, the NS isolates produced emulsions with lower K values,
438 suggesting a more fluid emulsion with less internal resistance to flow. This behavior can be
439 beneficial for applications requiring easy flow and spreadability, such as in liquid food products
440 or beverages. The decreased K values obtained in NS isolates might be attributed to variations
441 in protein structure and interaction with water, resulting in less resistance to flow.. This
442 discovery is consistent with earlier research that has found that protein type influences the
443 rheological qualities of emulsions [16,54,55].

444 Overall, the rheological properties of the emulsions are significantly influenced by the type of
 445 protein isolate used, with soybean proteins providing stronger and more viscous emulsions,
 446 while NS proteins offer more fluid and easily flowable emulsions. These findings are critical
 447 for tailoring emulsion properties to specific food applications, ensuring optimal performance
 448 and stability.

449 To further understand the flow behaviour of the emulsions, the flow curves were subjected to
 450 the Ostwald de Waele model. This model is well-suited for characterizing non-Newtonian fluids
 451 such as emulsions, where the connection between shear stress and shear rate is not linear. The
 452 model parameters, such as the consistency coefficient (K), and flow behaviour index (n), will
 453 offer more information on the emulsions' stability and texture [56]. Yield stress represents the
 454 stress required to initiate flow in a material. The soybean protein isolate SB6, with its high K
 455 value (194.6 mPa·sⁿ) and low n value (0.5184), suggests a strong and viscous emulsion with
 456 significant internal structure. Conversely, NS and CC isolates, with their lower K values,
 457 indicate more fluid emulsions with lower resistance to flow. This suggests that emulsions
 458 stabilized by SB6 are more rigid and require higher stress to flow, while NS isolates form more
 459 fluid emulsions with lower resistance to flow initiation [57].

460

461 **Table 2.**

462 Values for the parameters of Ostwald de Waele model in *Eq. 2*.

Sample	K [mPa sⁿ]	n	R²
Control	8.988±0.01 ^a	0.832±0.02 ^b	0.9976
CC6	9.95±0.15 ^b	0.8424±0.03 ^d	0.9991
CC8	11.62±0.05 ^a	0.8372±0.08 ^a	0.9949
CC10	10.82±0.02 ^a	0.8733±0.02 ^a	0.9990
NS6	11.33±0.05 ^a	0.7486±0.05 ^a	0.9881
NS8	8.885±0.03 ^a	0.7503±0.05 ^d	0.9934
NS10	6.871±0.10 ^b	0.8363±0.02 ^b	0.9964
SB6	194.6±0.02 ^c	0.5184±0.03 ^b	0.9816
SB8	82.35±0.06 ^a	0.727±0.01 ^c	0.9995
SB10	98.58±0.05 ^b	0.8658±0.03 ^d	0.5093
WB6	77.94±0.03 ^a	0.6704±0.2 ^b	0.9961
WB8	17.02±0.02 ^b	0.8619±0.02 ^b	0.9987
WB10	7.096±0.05 ^a	0.93±0.05 ^c	0.9975

463 Data are represented as mean \pm SD; different superscript letters indicate statistical significance
464 at $p \leq 0.05$.

465 **3.6. Stability and creaming index determination**

466 Emulsion stability is an important characteristic in the evaluation of emulsions because
467 it shows the emulsifier's capacity to keep the dispersed phase free of coalescence, flocculation,
468 and creaming throughout storage and application.

469 The emulsion stability (ES) of double emulsion samples stabilized by various protein
470 isolates was quantified post-centrifugation, with the results displayed in Table 3. NS isolates
471 (NS6, NS8, NS10) exhibited the highest stability, with NS10 achieving an ES of $85.09 \pm 1.30\%$.
472 Soybean protein isolates (SB6, SB8, SB10) presented varying levels of stability, with SB10
473 showing significantly lower stability ($22.49 \pm 0.34\%$) compared to other samples. The control
474 emulsion displayed an ES of $45.52 \pm 0.70\%$.

475 The results show that NS protein isolates had better emulsion stability than the other
476 plant proteins studied. According to the literature, emulsions stabilized with proteins, such as
477 those containing *Nigella sativa* protein, exhibit superior gelling and emulsifying properties,
478 which enhance the stability of the emulsion. The protein forms a thick interfacial layer around
479 the oil droplets, providing stabilization through both steric and electrostatic mechanisms.
480 *Nigella sativa* protein isolate has been found to possess high emulsification properties, foaming
481 stability, foaming capacity, and oil and water retention capabilities. These functional
482 characteristics contribute significantly to the remarkable stability of the emulsions stabilized by
483 *Nigella sativa* protein isolate [31,60]. .

484 Given status of soy protein as an efficient emulsifier, the much-decreased stability of
485 emulsions using soybean protein isolates, particularly SB10, is an unexpected conclusion. Teng
486 et al., [61] discovered that when the concentration of soy protein isolate increased over a
487 particular level, the protein molecules' ability to adsorb at the interface decreased, which
488 resulted in a reduction in the stability of the emulsion. They also discussed how the emulsion
489 stability dropped when protein aggregates were used in place of soy protein at the oil-water
490 interface. The aggregated protein molecules made it harder for water molecules to get through.
491 Soy proteins may experience partial denaturation or conformational changes during the
492 emulsification process, which could negatively impact the emulsifying properties of the
493 proteins[33].

494 The stability of the CC and WB isolates was moderate, greater than the control but lower
495 than the NS isolates. These findings show that, while these agricultural byproducts can be
496 utilized as emulsifiers, additional optimization may be required to improve their performance
497 to that of standard emulsifiers. Because the two main canola proteins, cruciferin, and napin
498 differ substantially in terms of their molecular structure, size, and physicochemical
499 characteristics, as well as their amino acid content, functional characteristics of canola protein
500 are highly dependent on their ratio. Canola proteins have not been used as extensively as they
501 could be as a beneficial food additive due to these complexities in their molecular structure and
502 composition [62]. In case of WB protein isolate, despite the fact that nutritional quality of
503 bioprocessed WB proteins has increased, the physicochemical properties of proteins govern
504 their usefulness in culinary applications [46]. Protein isolates from bran proteins such as oat
505 and rice have been widely researched and synthesized; however, the functional features of WB
506 proteins, particularly bioprocessed WB proteins, are little understood. Protein extractability
507 from WB and germ is affected by a variety of variables, including endosperm contamination,
508 encapsulation within cellular structures, and previous treatments such as defatting, heat
509 treatment, particle size reduction, and enzymatic treatment. This in-depth study of WB and
510 germ protein properties opens the door to increased utilization in a larger range of food
511 applications, particularly those requiring emulsion and stability [27,63].

512 The CI indicates how stable the emulsions are against phase separation during storage.
513 NS isolates (NS6, NS8) had the strongest creaming resistance, with a CI of $59.32 \pm 0.91\%$. The
514 CC isolates (CC6, CC8, CC10) came next, with a constant CI of $53.39 \pm 0.82\%$. The SB isolates
515 (SB6, SB8, SB10) demonstrated the lowest creaming resistance, with SB10 having a CI of
516 $17.80 \pm 0.27\%$, which is much lower than the CI of $23.73 \pm 0.36\%$ in the control sample.
517 The creaming index is a measure of the dispersed phase's propensity to move upwards, resulting
518 in a clean separation of the oil and aqueous phases. The density difference between the phases,
519 the viscosity of the continuous phase, and the size and distribution of the scattered droplets all
520 have an effect on this occurrence [64].

521 The comparatively high CI values for NS and CC indicate that these proteins can form
522 a stable film around droplets, avoiding coalescence and creaming. The low CI values obtained
523 for the soybean protein isolates, on the other hand, might be due to inadequate film strength or
524 flexibility, allowing the droplets to cluster and cream more easily. The constant CI throughout
525 the CC samples indicates consistent emulsion quality, but the heterogeneity found in the
526 soybean protein samples may represent changes in protein functioning or emulsion system
527 interactions [65,66].

529 3.7. Evaluating inclusion efficiency of anthocyanins

530 The IE reflects the percentage of anthocyanins that remained trapped within the inner aqueous
531 phase after centrifugation. The samples showed a high degree of anthocyanin inclusion overall,
532 with the SB8 sample displaying the highest inclusion efficiency at $92.86\pm 0.50\%$. The WB10
533 sample demonstrated the lowest IE at $87.62\pm 1.34\%$, yet this was still within a relatively high
534 range of efficiency. The control maintained an IE of $91.07\pm 1.40\%$, indicating that the tested
535 emulsifiers are comparably effective.

536 The efficiency of encapsulation is critical for emulsions' protective function in the transport of
537 bioactive substances such as anthocyanins, which are prone to degradation and loss during
538 processing and storage [67]. The higher inclusion efficiencies found across all samples indicate
539 that the protein isolates utilized can build a protective matrix around the anthocyanins,
540 preventing their leaking into the outer phase.

541 Soybean protein isolate SB8 had the greatest IE (92.86 ± 0.50), slightly higher than the control,
542 suggesting that it may provide a modestly superior encapsulation matrix for anthocyanins in
543 double emulsions. The isolates from WB, notably WB10, had a lower IE (87.62 ± 1.34) than the
544 other isolates, which might imply a less effective encapsulation capacity. The relatively small
545 differences in IE between protein samples might be related to unique interactions between
546 anthocyanins and proteins, which can impact binding affinity and encapsulation capabilities.
547 The highest inclusion efficiency in the SB8 sample implies that the specific circumstances or
548 components associated with this soybean protein isolate offer an ideal environment for
549 anthocyanin preservation [68–70]. The reduced efficiency in the WB10 sample might be
550 attributed to a less efficient protein network in limiting anthocyanin diffusion into the external
551 phase, which could be enhanced by altering protein content or emulsion processing settings
552 [71,72].

553 The findings suggest that the source of plant protein isolates might affect anthocyanin
554 microencapsulation performance. While all of the investigated protein isolates displayed
555 appropriate inclusion efficiencies, minor differences imply that optimizing the protein supply
556 and processing conditions might improve the stability and loading capacity of anthocyanin-
557 loaded double emulsions.

558 **Table 3.**

559 Comparative analysis of emulsion stability, creaming index, droplet size distribution,
 560 encapsulation efficiency, and viscosity of different protein-stabilized emulsions

Samples	ES(%)	CI(%)	SPAN	CE Diameter (4,3) (µm)	IE (%)
Control	45.52±0.70 ^c	23.73±0.36 ^c	1.49±0.02 ^f	66.01±1.01 ^e	91.07±1.40 ^{ab}
SB6	53.28±0.82 ^d	29.66±0.45 ^d	1.22±0.02 ^{ab}	85.97±1.32 ⁱ	89.91±1.38 ^{ab}
SB8	41.24±0.63 ^b	20.76±0.32 ^b	1.17±0.02 ^a	58.77±0.90 ^d	92.86±0.50 ^b
SB10	22.49±0.34 ^a	17.80±0.27 ^a	3.16±0.05 ^h	86.43±1.32 ⁱ	92.82±1.42 ^b
CC6	61.37±0.94 ^{gh}	53.39±0.82 ^g	1.38±0.02 ^{de}	73.16±1.12 ^g	90.80±1.39 ^{ab}
CC8	62.57±0.96 ^h	53.39±0.82 ^g	1.24±0.02 ^{ab}	64.99±1.00 ^e	91.01±1.39 ^{ab}
CC10	55.95±0.86 ^{de}	53.39±0.82 ^g	1.40±0.02 ^e	74.55±1.14 ^g	90.84±1.39 ^{ab}
NS6	75.89±1.16 ⁱ	59.32±0.91 ^h	1.26±0.02 ^{bc}	34.59±0.53 ^b	91.06±1.40 ^{ab}
NS8	77.26±1.18 ⁱ	59.32±0.91 ^h	1.32±0.02 ^{cd}	27.40±0.42 ^a	90.10±1.38 ^{ab}
NS10	85.09±1.30 ^j	53.39±0.82 ^g	1.40±0.02 ^e	49.35±0.76 ^c	89.51±1.37 ^{ab}
WB6	59.07±0.91 ^{fg}	41.53±0.64 ^e	2.44±0.04 ^g	78.31±1.20 ^h	89.89±1.38 ^{ab}
WB8	57.73±0.88 ^{ef}	41.53±0.64 ^e	1.17±0.02 ^a	75.70±1.16 ^{gh}	90.14±1.38 ^{ab}
WB10	63.84±0.98 ^h	47.46±0.73 ^f	1.19±0.02 ^{ab}	69.38±1.06 ^f	87.62±1.34 ^a

561 ES = Emulsion Stability; CI = Creaming Index; SPAN = Span of the droplet size distribution;
 562 IE = Efficiency of Inclusion; η = Apparent Viscosity. Data are represented as mean \pm SD;
 563 different superscript letters indicate statistical significance at $p \leq 0.05$.

564

565

566 3.8. Assessment of color

567 Color measurements of the emulsions were taken to obtain L* (lightness), a* (red-green axis),
 568 and b* (yellow-blue axis) values according to the CIE Lab color space. Based on the results,
 569 for lightness (L*), the control sample had the highest value, suggesting a lighter color
 570 characteristic. In comparison, protein isolates showed varying degrees of lightness, with NS
 571 concentrates exhibiting notably lower L* values, indicating a darker appearance, which could
 572 influence the color perception of the emulsions. CC concentrates demonstrated moderate
 573 lightness, with CC8 being the darkest within this group. SB isolates generally showed higher
 574 lightness, closer to the control, with SB10 being the lightest among all protein isolates. WB
 575 isolates had L* values indicating a light appearance, although not as light as the control. The L*
 576 values of samples were considerably lower than the control, which might be explained by the
 577 inclusion of encapsulated anthocyanin powders [73].

578 SB6 had a considerably negative value for the b* value, reflecting the yellow-blue color
 579 spectrum, showing a leaning towards blue, which is distinct from other samples that had

580 positive b* values, indicating yellow tones. WB isolates exhibited somewhat positive b* values,
 581 with WB8 having the most yellow. CC concentrates also had positive b* values, with CC6
 582 having the most yellowness. The color characteristics of protein isolates can have a considerable
 583 impact on the overall look of food items. The dark color of NS concentrates may be
 584 advantageous in goods requiring a darker hue, whilst the brighter color of SB isolates may be
 585 preferable for lighter-colored emulsions. The dark color of the NS samples was generated by
 586 phenolic chemicals. The primary phenolic components in blackseed are epicatechin and rutin
 587 [54]. By recognizing the inherent red color of anthocyanins, the redness in NS and SB isolates
 588 might possibly improve the visual attractiveness of anthocyanin-emulsified goods. The
 589 yellowish tone indicated by the b* values in CC and WB isolates, on the other hand, may need
 590 to be considered since it may alter the desired color output of the final product.

591

592 **Table 4.** CIE Lab color parameters of emulsion samples

Samples	L*	a*	b*
Control	80.29±0.68 ^h	10.94±0.16 ^b	1.40±0.03 ^d
SB6	69.94±0.29 ^{cd}	19.31±0.18 ⁱ	-5.17±0.13 ^a
SB8	73.12±0.60 ^f	14.17±0.17 ^c	-3.30±0.08 ^b
SB10	77.00±0.64 ^g	7.82±0.15 ^a	-2.64±0.04 ^c
CC6	70.85±0.64 ^{de}	11.95±0.06 ^c	6.33±0.10 ^k
CC8	68.81±1.31 ^c	13.06±0.36 ^d	5.00±0.13 ^j
CC10	71.02±1.10 ^{de}	11.72±0.19 ^c	4.42±0.15 ^{hi}
NS6	59.06±0.29 ^a	18.81±0.11 ⁱ	5.11±0.18 ^j
NS8	58.62±0.12 ^a	17.53±0.17 ^h	4.74±0.21 ^{ij}
NS10	65.88±0.61 ^b	15.86±0.17 ^g	4.14±0.06 ^{fh}
WB6	72.62±0.28 ^{ef}	15.10±0.18 ^f	2.85±0.28 ^c
WB8	71.50±0.55 ^{def}	14.37±0.05 ^c	3.35±0.19 ^f
WB10	71.22±0.51 ^{def}	10.72±0.08 ^b	3.87±0.25 ^f

593 Data are represented as mean ± SD; different superscript letters indicate statistical significance
 594 at p ≤ 0.05.

595

596

597 **4. Conclusions**

598 This work comprehensively investigated the efficiency of plant protein isolates obtained from
 599 CC, NS, and WB as new emulsifiers for the microencapsulation of anthocyanins in double

600 emulsion systems. The research has offered substantial insights into the possible application of
601 these by-product-derived protein isolates in food technology using a range of analytical
602 processes such as colorimetric analysis, inclusion efficiency evaluation, and FTIR. Based on
603 the ES results, NS concentrates were particularly successful at producing stable emulsions,
604 which might be related to their flexible protein structures. Droplet size study demonstrated that
605 soybean protein isolates created smaller and more uniform droplets, indicating their potential
606 for making stable emulsions under optimized circumstances. The inclusion efficiency indicated
607 that all protein isolates had good inclusion efficiencies, with soybean isolates having especially
608 high values, indicating their potential for successfully delivering bioactive chemicals. These
609 findings were supported by apparent viscosity measurements, which showed that soybean
610 protein isolates contributed to greater viscosity emulsions, which is frequently linked with
611 enhanced emulsion stability. The secondary structure of the proteins was revealed by FT-IR
612 analysis, which revealed that the CC concentrates were largely beta-sheets, the NS concentrates
613 were random coils, and the WB isolates were a mix of alpha-helices and beta-sheets. These
614 structural characteristics may be connected with the reported functional capabilities, providing
615 a foundation for selecting optimal protein isolates for specific dietary applications.
616 The findings of this work emphasize the potential for agricultural by-product-derived proteins
617 to be used as sustainable alternatives to traditional emulsifiers in food applications, notably for
618 the encapsulation and delivery of sensitive bioactive chemicals such as anthocyanins.
619 Furthermore, this study supports the notion that valorizing agricultural byproducts might help
620 to ensure sustainable food production by giving useful components to the food sector.
621 Future study should investigate the long-term stability of emulsions, the bioavailability of the
622 encapsulated components, and the sensory properties of the final product. Such research will
623 help to cement the position of plant-based proteins in the production of functional foods and
624 contribute to the agriculture sector's circular economy.

625 **5. Acknowledgements**

626 The work was performed within the framework of the project "Coacervation of double
627 emulsions with anthocyanins using plant-based proteins" funded by the SONATA program of
628 the National Science Center - project no: 2021/43/D/NZ9/01572.

629 I extend my heartfelt gratitude to Prof. Dr. Sülhattin Yaşar whose expertise and timely analysis
630 using FT-IR were invaluable to the research presented in this paper. His willingness to provide
631 guidance and support throughout this process is deeply appreciated. I am thankful for his
632 generous contribution and for sharing his profound knowledge and resources.

634 **References**

- 635 [1] E. Álvarez-Castillo, M. Felix, C. Bengoechea, A. Guerrero, Proteins from agri-food
636 industrial biowastes or co-products and their applications as green materials, *Foods* 10
637 (2021) 981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10050981>.
- 638 [2] M. Kurek, N. Benaida-Debbache, I.E. Garofulić, K. Galić, S. Avallone, A. Voilley, Y.
639 Waché, Antioxidants and Bioactive Compounds in Food: Critical Review of Issues and
640 Prospects, *Antioxidants* 11 (2022) 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11040742>.
- 641 [3] N. Kanha, J.M. Regenstein, S. Surawang, P. Pitchakarn, T. Laokuldilok, Properties and
642 kinetics of the in vitro release of anthocyanin-rich microcapsules produced through
643 spray and freeze-drying complex coacervated double emulsions, *Food Chem.* 340
644 (2021) 127950. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.127950>.
- 645 [4] M.A. Alam, P. Islam, N. Subhan, M.M. Rahman, F. Khan, G.E. Burrows, L. Nahar,
646 S.D. Sarker, Potential health benefits of anthocyanins in oxidative stress related
647 disorders, Springer Netherlands, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11101-021-09757-1>.
- 648 [5] D. V. Mikhailova, O.G. Shevchenko, D.A. Golubev, E.Y. Platonova, N. V. Zemskaya,
649 O.Y. Shoeva, E.I. Gordeeva, S.A. Patov, M. V. Shaposhnikov, E.K. Khlestkina, A.
650 Moskalev, Antioxidant Properties and Geroprotective Potential of Wheat Bran Extracts
651 with Increased Content of Anthocyanins, *Antioxidants* 12 (2023) 2010.
652 <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox12112010>.
- 653 [6] Y. Chen, T. Belwal, Y. Xu, Q. Ma, D. Li, L. Li, H. Xiao, Z. Luo, Updated insights into
654 anthocyanin stability behavior from bases to cases: Why and why not anthocyanins
655 lose during food processing, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 63 (2023) 8639–8671.
656 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2022.2063250>.
- 657 [7] J.M. Alvarez-Suarez, C. Cuadrado, I.B. Redondo, F. Giampieri, A.M. González-
658 Paramás, C. Santos-Buelga, Novel approaches in anthocyanin research - Plant
659 fortification and bioavailability issues, *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 117 (2021) 92–105.
660 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2021.01.049>.
- 661 [8] F. Heidari, S.M. Jafari, A.M. Ziaifar, N. Malekjani, Stability and release mechanisms
662 of double emulsions loaded with bioactive compounds; a critical review, *Adv. Colloid
663 Interface Sci.* 299 (2022) 102567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2021.102567>.

- 664 [9] A. Kumar, R. Kaur, V. Kumar, S. Kumar, R. Gehlot, P. Aggarwal, New insights into
665 water-in-oil-in-water (W/O/W) double emulsions: Properties, fabrication, instability
666 mechanism, and food applications, *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 128 (2022) 22–37.
667 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2022.07.016>.
- 668 [10] A.C. Karaca, N. Low, M. Nickerson, Emulsifying properties of canola and flaxseed
669 protein isolates produced by isoelectric precipitation and salt extraction, *Food Res. Int.*
670 44 (2011) 2991–2998. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2011.07.009>.
- 671 [11] Y.R. Tang, S. Ghosh, Stability and rheology of canola protein isolate-stabilized
672 concentrated oil-in-water emulsions, *Food Hydrocoll.* 113 (2021) 106399.
- 673 [12] D. Lv, F. Chen, L. Yin, P. Zhang, M.T. Rashid, J. Yu, Wheat bran arabinoxylan-
674 soybean protein isolate emulsion-filled gels as a β -carotene delivery carrier: Effect of
675 polysaccharide content on textural and rheological properties, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*
676 253 (2023) 126465.
- 677 [13] I. Frosi, L. Ferron, R. Colombo, A. Papetti, Natural carriers: Recent advances in their
678 use to improve the stability and bioaccessibility of food active compounds, *Crit. Rev.*
679 *Food Sci. Nutr.* 0 (2022) 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2022.2157371>.
- 680 [14] I. Dreoni, Z. Matthews, M. Schaafsma, The impacts of soy production on multi-
681 dimensional well-being and ecosystem services: A systematic review, *J. Clean. Prod.*
682 335 (2022) 130182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.130182>.
- 683 [15] A. Chmielewska, M. Kozłowska, D. Rachwał, P. Wnukowski, R. Amarowicz, E.
684 Nebesny, J. Rosicka-Kaczmarek, Canola/rapeseed protein–nutritional value,
685 functionality and food application: a review, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 61 (2021)
686 3836–3856. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2020.1809342>.
- 687 [16] I. Trigui, H. Yaich, A. Sila, S. Cheikh, R. Fatma, K. Ali, B. Hamadi, Physical , techno -
688 functional and antioxidant properties of black cumin seeds protein isolate and
689 hydrolysates, *J. Food Meas. Charact.* 15 (2021) 3491–3500.
690 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11694-021-00935-5>.
- 691 [17] Y. Yamasaki, H. Konno, K. Noda, Polyphenol oxidase from wheat bran is a serpin,
692 *Acta Biochim. Pol.* 55 (2008) 325–328. https://doi.org/10.18388/abp.2008_3079.
- 693 [18] J. Chandrasekhar, M.C. Madhusudhan, K.S.M.S. Raghavarao, Extraction of

- 694 anthocyanins from red cabbage and purification using adsorption, *Food Bioprod.*
695 *Process.* 90 (2012) 615–623. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbp.2012.07.004>.
- 696 [19] B. Sobti, A. Kamal-Eldin, S. Rasul, M.S.K. Alnuaimi, K.J.J. Alnuaimi, A.A.K.
697 Alhassani, M.M.A. Almheiri, A. Nazir, Encapsulation Properties of *Mentha piperita*
698 Leaf Extracts Prepared Using an Ultrasound-Assisted Double Emulsion Method, *Foods*
699 12 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12091838>.
- 700 [20] M.M. Bradford, A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram
701 quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding, *Anal. Biochem.* 72
702 (1976) 248–254. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697\(76\)90527-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697(76)90527-3).
- 703 [21] A. Onopiuk, A. Półtorak, D.-W. Sun, A. Wierzbicka, Effects of selected myofibrillar
704 protein activities on beef tenderization process based on electrophoretic analysis, *J.*
705 *Food Process Eng.* 41 (2018) e12596. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfpe.12596>.
- 706 [22] S. Karp, J. Wyrwicz, M.A. Kurek, Comparative analysis of the physical properties of
707 o/w emulsions stabilised by cereal β -glucan and other stabilisers, *Int. J. Biol.*
708 *Macromol.* 132 (2019) 236–243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.03.212>.
- 709 [23] M. Yildirim, G. Sumnu, S. Sahin, The effects of emulsifier type, phase ratio, and
710 homogenization methods on stability of the double emulsion, *J. Dispers. Sci. Technol.*
711 38 (2017) 807–814. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01932691.2016.1201768>.
- 712 [24] E. Hady, M. Youssef, A.H. Aljahani, H. Aljumayi, K.A. Ismail, E.S. El-Damaty, R.
713 Sami, G. El-Sharnouby, Enhancement of the Stability of Encapsulated Pomegranate
714 (*Punica granatum L.*) Peel Extract by Double Emulsion with Carboxymethyl Cellulose,
715 *Crystals* 12 (2022) 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst12050622>.
- 716 [25] D. de Almeida Paula, A. Mota Ramos, E. Basílio de Oliveira, E. Maurício Furtado
717 Martins, F. Augusto Ribeiro de Barros, M. Cristina Teixeira Ribeiro Vidigal, N. de
718 Almeida Costa, C. Tatagiba da Rocha, Increased thermal stability of anthocyanins at
719 pH 4.0 by guar gum in aqueous dispersions and in double emulsions W/O/W, *Int. J.*
720 *Biol. Macromol.* 117 (2018) 665–672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.05.219>.
- 721 [26] M.A. Rahim, A. Shoukat, W. Khalid, A. Ejaz, N. Itrat, I. Majeed, H. Koraqi, M. Imran,
722 M.U. Nisa, A. Nazir, W.S. Alansari, A.A. Eskandrani, G. Shamlan, A. Al-farga,
723 Encapsulation Processes , Fatty Acid Profiles , Oxidative Stability , and Medicinal
724 Properties of Black Seed (*Nigella sativa*), *Foods* 11 (2022) 2826.

- 725 [27] R.R. Balandrán-Quintana, J.N. Mercado-Ruiz, A.M. Mendoza-Wilson, Wheat Bran
726 Proteins: A Review of Their Uses and Potential, *Food Rev. Int.* 31 (2015) 279–293.
727 <https://doi.org/10.1080/87559129.2015.1015137>.
- 728 [28] D.J. McClements, S.M. Jafari, Improving emulsion formation, stability and
729 performance using mixed emulsifiers: A review, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* 251 (2018)
730 55–79. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2017.12.001>.
- 731 [29] W. Kim, Y. Wang, C. Selomulya, Dairy and plant proteins as natural food emulsifiers,
732 *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 105 (2020) 261–272.
733 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2020.09.012>.
- 734 [30] P. Shen, J. Yang, C. V. Nikiforidis, H.C.M. Mocking-Bode, L.M.C. Sagis, Cruciferin
735 versus napin – Air-water interface and foam stabilizing properties of rapeseed storage
736 proteins, *Food Hydrocoll.* 136 (2023) 108300.
737 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2022.108300>.
- 738 [31] D. Kadam, A. Kadam, K. Tungare, P. Arte, S.S. Lele, An investigation of correlation
739 between structural and functional properties of *Nigella sativa* protein isolate, *J. Food*
740 *Biochem.* 46 (2022) 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfbc.14391>.
- 741 [32] N. De Brier, S. V. Gomand, I. Celus, C.M. Courtin, K. Brijs, J.A. Delcour,
742 Extractability and Chromatographic Characterization of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.)
743 Bran Protein, *J. Food Sci.* 80 (2015) C967–C974. [https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-](https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.12856)
744 [3841.12856](https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.12856).
- 745 [33] L. Zhang, Q. Li, W. Zhang, S. Bakalis, Y. Luo, R. Lametsch, Different source of
746 commercial soy protein isolates: Structural, compositional, and physicochemical
747 characteristics in relation to protein functionalities, *Food Chem.* 433 (2024) 137315.
- 748 [34] H. Zhang, X. Zhao, X. Chen, X. Xu, Thoroughly review the recent progresses in
749 improving O/W interfacial properties of proteins through various strategies, *Front.*
750 *Nutr.* 9 (2022) 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2022.1043809>.
- 751 [35] B. Kupikowska-Stobba, J. Domagała, M.M. Kasprzak, Critical Review of Techniques
752 for Food Emulsion Characterization, *Appl. Sci.* 14 (2024) 1069.
753 <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14031069>.
- 754 [36] R.R. Lima, R. Stephani, Í.T. Perrone, A.F. de Carvalho, Plant-based proteins: A review

- 755 of factors modifying the protein structure and affecting emulsifying properties, *Food*
756 *Chem. Adv.* 3 (2023) 100397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.focha.2023.100397>.
- 757 [37] L. Li, H. He, D. Wu, D. Lin, W. Qin, D. Meng, R. Yang, Q. Zhang, Rheological and
758 textural properties of acid-induced soybean protein isolate gel in the presence of
759 soybean protein isolate hydrolysates or their glycosylated products, *Food Chem.* 360
760 (2021) 129991.
- 761 [38] A. Borba, A. Gómez-Zavaglia, Infrared spectroscopy: an underexploited analytical tool
762 for assessing physicochemical properties of food products and processing, *Curr. Opin.*
763 *Food Sci.* 49 (2023) 100953. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2022.100953>.
- 764 [39] M. Ghasemi, S. Habibian-Dehkordi, S. Farhadian, Change in thermal stability and
765 molecular structure characteristics of whey protein beta-lactoglobulin upon the
766 interaction with levamisole hydrochloride, *Food Chem.* 431 (2024) 137073.
767 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2023.137073>.
- 768 [40] W.M.S. Gomaa, X. Feng, H. Zhang, X. Zhang, W. Zhang, X. Yan, Q. Peng, P. Yu,
769 Application of advanced molecular spectroscopy and modern evaluation techniques in
770 canola molecular structure and nutrition property research, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.*
771 61 (2021) 3256–3266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2020.1798343>.
- 772 [41] Y. Zhou, S.P. Petrova, K.J. Edgar, Chemical synthesis of polysaccharide–protein and
773 polysaccharide–peptide conjugates: A review, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 274 (2021) 118662.
774 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2021.118662>.
- 775 [42] I. Trigui, H. Yaich, A. Zouari, S. Cheikh-Rouhou, C. Blecker, H. Attia, M.A. Ayadi,
776 Structure-function relationship of black cumin seeds protein isolates: Amino-acid
777 profiling, surface characteristics, and thermal properties, *Food Struct.* 29 (2021)
778 100203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foostr.2021.100203>.
- 779 [43] H. Zhu, L. Wang, X. Li, J. Shi, M. Scanlon, S. Xue, M. Nosworthy, N. Vafaei, Canola
780 Seed Protein: Pretreatment, Extraction, Structure, Physicochemical and Functional
781 Characteristics, *Foods* 13 (2024) 1357. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13091357>.
- 782 [44] N. Devi, D. Hazarika, C. Deka, D.K. Kakati, Study of complex coacervation of gelatin
783 a and sodium alginate for microencapsulation of olive oil, *J. Macromol. Sci. Part A*
784 *Pure Appl. Chem.* 49 (2012) 936–945. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10601325.2012.722854>.

- 785 [45] J.G. Luna-Valdez, R.R. Baladrán-Quintana, J.A. Azamar-Barrios, A.M. Mendoza-
786 Wilson, G. Ramos-Clamont Montfort, A spectroscopic approach to determine the
787 formation mechanism of biopolymer particles from wheat bran proteins, *J. Mol. Struct.*
788 1224 (2021) 129194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2020.129194>.
- 789 [46] E. Arte, X. Huang, E. Nordlund, K. Katina, Biochemical characterization and
790 technofunctional properties of bioprocessed wheat bran protein isolates, *Food Chem.*
791 289 (2019) 103–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2019.03.020>.
- 792 [47] F. Shahidi, C.S. Dissanayaka, Phenolic-protein interactions: insight from in-silico
793 analyses – a review, *Food Prod. Process. Nutr.* 5 (2023).
794 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43014-022-00121-0>.
- 795 [48] H. Qian, F. Guo, H. Xiong, H. Zhang, L. Jiang, Y. Sun, The Interactional
796 Characterization of Lentil Protein Isolate (LPI) with Cyanidin-3-O-Glucoside (C3G)
797 and Their Effect on the Stability and Antioxidant Activity of C3G, *Foods* 12 (2022)
798 104. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12010104>.
- 799 [49] N.A. Mir, M. Bharadwaj, B. Yousuf, K. Gul, C.S. Riar, S. Singh, Food Biopolymers:
800 Structural, Functional, and Nutraceutical Properties: Food Proteins: An Overview, in:
801 *Food Biopolym. Struct. Funct. Nutraceutical Prop.*, 2021: pp. 211–229.
802 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27061-2_9.
- 803 [50] M.E. Pitz, A.M. Nukovic, M.A. Elpers, A.A. Alexander-Bryant, Factors Affecting
804 Secondary and Supramolecular Structures of Self-Assembling Peptide Nanocarriers,
805 *Macromol. Biosci.* 22 (2022) 2100347. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mabi.202100347>.
- 806 [51] N. Leister, H.P. Karbstein, Evaluating the Stability of Double Emulsions — A Review
807 of the Measurement Techniques for the Systematic Investigation of Instability
808 Mechanisms, *Colloids and Interfaces* 4 (2020) 1–18.
- 809 [52] R. Liu, X. Yan, R. Liu, Q. Wu, Y. Gao, E.M. Muhindo, Z. Zhi, T. Wu, W. Sui, M.
810 Zhang, Lima bean (*Phaseolus lunatus* Linn.) protein isolate as a promising plant protein
811 mixed with xanthan gum for stabilizing oil-in-water emulsions, *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 104
812 (2023) 818–828.
- 813 [53] T.D.O. Flynn, S.A. Hogan, D.F.M. Daly, J.A.O. Mahony, N.A. Mccarthy, Rheological
814 and Solubility Properties of Soy Protein Isolate, *Molecules* 26 (2021) 3015.

- 815 [54] M. Kasprzak, E. Jamróz, N. Nowak, W. Grzebieniarz, J. Tkaczewska, Design of triple-
816 layer films with blackseed protein as dispersion or emulsion, *Food Chem.* 435 (2024)
817 137533.
- 818 [55] S. Makouie, M. Alizadeh, A. Khosrowshahi, Optimization of Wall Components for
819 Encapsulation of *Nigella Sativa* Seed Oil by Freeze-Drying, *Indones. Food Sci.*
820 *Technol. J.* 3 (2019) 1–9.
- 821 [56] R.I. Dekker, H.V.M. Kibbelaar, A. Deblais, D. Bonn, Rheology of emulsions with
822 polymer solutions as the continuous phase, *J. Non-Newtonian Fluid Mech.* 310 (2022)
823 104938.
- 824 [57] C. Luan, Q. Yang, X. Lin, X. Gao, H. Cheng, Y. Huang, P. Du, Z. Zhou, J. Wang, The
825 Synergistic Effects of Ultrafine Slag Powder and Limestone on the Rheology Behavior,
826 Microstructure, and Fractal Features of Ultra-High Performance Concrete (UHPC),
827 *Materials (Basel)*. 16 (2023) 2281. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16062281>.
- 828 [58] M. Pattnaik, H.N. Mishra, Effect of Ultrasonication and wall materials on the stability,
829 rheology, and encapsulation efficiency of vitamins in a lipid-based double emulsion
830 template, *J. Food Process Eng.* 46 (2023) e14201. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfpe.14201>.
- 831 [59] S. Ansari, M.A.I. Rashid, P.R. Waghmare, D.S. Nobes, Measurement of the flow
832 behavior index of Newtonian and shear-thinning fluids via analysis of the flow velocity
833 characteristics in a mini-channel, *SN Appl. Sci.* 2 (2020) 1787.
834 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-03561-w>.
- 835 [60] Y. Xu, L. Sun, Y. Zhuang, Y. Gu, G. Cheng, X. Fan, Y. Ding, H. Liu, Protein-
836 Stabilized Emulsion Gels with Improved Emulsifying and Gelling Properties for the
837 Delivery of Bioactive Ingredients: A Review, *Foods* 12 (2023).
838 <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12142703>.
- 839 [61] F. Teng, M. He, J. Xu, F. Chen, C. Wu, Z. Wang, Y. Li, Effect of ultrasonication on the
840 stability and storage of a soy protein isolate-phosphatidylcholine nanoemulsions, *Sci.*
841 *Rep.* 10 (2020) 14010. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-70462-8>.
- 842 [62] Y.R. Tang, S. Ghosh, A Review of the Utilization of Canola Protein as an Emulsifier in
843 the Development of Food Emulsions, *Molecules* 28 (2023) 8086.
- 844 [63] F. Janssen, C.M. Courtin, A.G.B. Wouters, Aqueous phase extractable protein of wheat

- 845 bran and germ for the production of liquid and semi-solid foods, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci.*
846 *Nutr.* 0 (2023) 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2023.2214615>.
- 847 [64] D.J. McClements, J. Lu, L. Grossmann, Proposed Methods for Testing and Comparing
848 the Emulsifying Properties of Proteins from Animal, Plant, and Alternative Sources,
849 *Colloids and Interfaces* 6 (2022) 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/colloids6020019>.
- 850 [65] S. Yan, F. Xie, S. Zhang, L. Jiang, B. Qi, Y. Li, Effects of soybean protein isolate –
851 polyphenol conjugate formation on the protein structure and emulsifying properties:
852 Protein – polyphenol emulsification performance in the presence of chitosan, *Colloids*
853 *Surfaces A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 609 (2021).
854 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2020.125641>.
- 855 [66] N. Nourmohammadi, L. Austin, D. Chen, Protein-Based Fat Replacers: A Focus on
856 Fabrication Methods and Fat-Mimic Mechanisms, *Foods* 12 (2023) 957.
857 <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12050957>.
- 858 [67] A.K. Rashwan, N. Karim, Y. Xu, J. Xie, H. Cui, M.R. Mozafari, W. Chen, Potential
859 micro-/nano-encapsulation systems for improving stability and bioavailability of
860 anthocyanins: An updated review, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 0 (2021) 1–24.
861 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2021.1987858>.
- 862 [68] H. Wu, G. Oliveira, M.A. Lila, Protein-binding approaches for improving
863 bioaccessibility and bioavailability of anthocyanins, *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.*
864 22 (2023) 333–354. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.13070>.
- 865 [69] Y. Wu, Z. Yin, X. Qie, Y. Chen, M. Zeng, Z. Wang, F. Qin, J. Chen, Z. He, Interaction
866 of soy protein isolate hydrolysates with cyanidin-3-o-glucoside and its effect on the in
867 vitro antioxidant capacity of the complexes under neutral condition, *Molecules* 26
868 (2021) 1721. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26061721>.
- 869 [70] J. Song, Y. Yu, M. Chen, Z. Ren, L. Chen, C. Fu, Z. feei Ma, Z. Li, Advancement of
870 Protein- and Polysaccharide-Based Biopolymers for Anthocyanin Encapsulation, *Front.*
871 *Nutr.* 9 (2022) 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2022.938829>.
- 872 [71] N. Sharma, A. Kumari, V. Chunduri, S. Kaur, J. Banda, A. Goyal, M. Garg,
873 Anthocyanin biofortified black, blue and purple wheat exhibited lower amino acid
874 cooking losses than white wheat, *LWT* 154 (2022) 112802.
875 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2021.112802>.

- 876 [72] Z. Guo, Y. Huang, J. Huang, S. Li, Z. Zhu, Q. Deng, S. Cheng, Formation of protein-
877 anthocyanin complex induced by grape skin extracts interacting with wheat gliadins:
878 Multi-spectroscopy and molecular docking analysis, *Food Chem.* 385 (2022) 132702.
879 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2022.132702>.
- 880 [73] O.E. Constantin, N. Stănciuc, Y. Yan, I.O. Ghinea, C. Ungureanu, A. Cîrciumaru, D.
881 Wang, N. Poklar Ulrih, G. Râpeanu, Polymers and protein-associated vesicles for the
882 microencapsulation of anthocyanins from grape skins used for food applications, *J. Sci.*
883 *Food Agric.* 101 (2021) 2676–2686. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.10892>.
- 884